

Digital Preservation Record: Audio Recording

Rahim Thawer - Queer Mental Health Media Archive

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Abstract

Podcast discussion expanding on the clinical concepts of shame and sexuality in queer experiences. Examines how early shaming messages shape adult sexual expression and intimacy patterns. Provides therapeutic frameworks for identifying and transforming shame-based narratives about desire, pleasure, and relationship formation. Addresses specific shame dynamics in LGBTQ+ contexts and pathways to sexual liberation.

Keywords

shame, sexuality, clinical practice

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